

4Q27 (4QNum^b) frag. 42 + PAM 43.680 frag. 27 (Num 26:64-65)

Eibert Tigchelaar, KU Leuven

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The unidentified fragment PAM 43.680 frag. 27 (DJD 33, plate XXI) should be joined to 4Q27 (4QNum^b) frag. 42, in lines 1-2. The fragment is no longer located on IAA Plate 71, and I am not aware of its present location. Based on the old PAM 43.680 photograph—for which I used <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285459>—the fragment joins perfectly with the Numbers fragment.

One may transcribe 4Q27 col. XXI frag. 42-47 lines 1-2 + PAM 43.680 frag. 27 now as follows:

מושה ואהרון הכוהן אשר פקדו את בני ישראל ב[מדבר סִיני כִּי־אֵא אִמְרָן] יִהְיֶה 1
להמה מות ימותו במדבר ולוא נות[ר מֵהֶם אִישׁ] כ[יֵא אִם כֵּלֵב בֶּן יִפֹּנִיָה וַיִּהְיֶה שׁוֹעַ 2

The contribution of the newly identified to the edition of the manuscript is minimal. It provides a few more letters which were expected on the basis of the known text of Numbers. It does, however, confirm the editor's assumption that line 1 is the first line of the column (DJD 12, p. 242).

References

- DJD 12 Eugene Ulrich, ed., *Qumran Cave 4. VII: Genesis to Numbers*. Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 12 (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1994)
- DJD 33 Dana M. Pike and Andrew C. Skinner, eds., *Qumran Cave 4. XXIII: Unidentified Fragments*. Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 33 (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001)
- IAA Israel Antiquities Authority
- PAM Palestine Archaeological Museum